

Review Article

TROPICSAFE project: detection and management of lethal yellowing and grapevine yellows diseases in partner countries

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Abstract

The confirmation of the presence of 16SrXXII-B phytoplasmas associated with coconut lethal yellowing disease in Ghana and of 16SrIV in the Caribbean (Jamaica, Cuba, and Mexico) were the basis to study alternative plant species and potential insect vectors of this economically relevant disease carried out by the TROPICSAFE project started in 2017. In South Africa grapevine yellows disease associated with '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma asteris', (subgroup 16SrI-B) and transmitted by the leafhopper *Mgenia fuscovaria* was studied in its main epidemiological aspects that are relevant to its management. In Chile and in Italy phytoplasmas belonging to diverse ribosomal subgroups and several alternative host plants were detected. Some insect species have been described as phytoplasma vectors or potential vectors in grapevine or in vineyard environments.

Keywords: plant diseases, insect transmission, epidemiology, management

Introduction

The TROPICSAFE project is studying some of the diseases associated with phloem-limited bacteria in coconut palms, grapevine, and citrus species in diverse countries. It started in May 2017 and had one year prolongation due to the covid-19 pandemic, so it will end in April 2022 (<http://www.tropicsafe.eu/>). A part for the citrus "huanglongbing" disease associated with the presence of '*Candidatus* Liberibacter' species, mainly studied in Cuba, France (Guadeloupe), South Africa and Spain (where one of the known insect vector, *Trioza eritreae* is present), the project studies the epidemiology and management of coconut palms and grapevine associated phytoplasma diseases. Coconut palm lethal yellowing is studied in Ghana, Cuba, Jamaica and Mexico and grapevine yellows are studied

in Italy, South Africa, and Chile (Figure 1). The presence and the identity of the pathogen strains present in the different countries was verified through their molecular characterization and in some cases also cultivation in artificial media to acquire the data necessary to detect and manage, in a sustainable manner, the studied diseases. The pathogen identification in alternative host plants and insects vectors and potential vectors was also obtained together with the improvement of specific diagnostic techniques.

Coconut lethal yellowing

Surveys in Africa resulted in the identification of '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma palmicola'-related strains (16SrXXII-A and -B) in coconut palms showing lethal yellowing (LY) disease in Mozambique and in Ghana,

respectively (Figure 1); while in Cuba, Jamaica, and Mexico (Figure 2) the 16SrIV phytoplasma group was confirmed as associated with the disease (Gurr *et al.*, 2016; Paredes-Tomás *et al.*, 2019; Hernandez *et al.*, 2020). In Jamaica where the LY disease has been managed since a number of years with sustainable results (Myrie *et al.*, 2011) the newly discovered insect species *Oecleus*

mackaspringii was associated with coconut palm in plots with still active cases of the disease (Figure 3) acting as possible vector (Myrie *et al.*, 2019). In Cuba, the phytoplasma was detected in coconut palms with lethal yellowing; however, also symptomatic palms positive for phytoplasmas belonging to the ribosomal groups 16SrI, 16SrVII and 16SrXII were identified

Figure 1. From left: the geographical distribution of the countries participating in the TROPICSAFE project and dead coconut palms resulting from infection with the 16SrXXII-B 'Candidatus Phytoplasma palmicola' in Ghana (F. Pilet, Cirad, France).

Figure 2. Symptoms of lethal yellowing: nut drop (A), inflorescence necrosis (B), leaf yellowing (C) and loss of foliage leaving the bare trunk (D) (M. Narváez *et al.*, CICY, Mexico).

Figure 3. From left: symptomatic coconut tree and removal of lethal yellowing infected tree and collection of insects from the leaves of the removed trees in Jamaica (W. Myrie, CIB, Jamaica).

(Paredes-Tomás *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, in citrus infected with “huanglongbing” the 16SrIV phytoplasma was found mainly in mixed infection with ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*’ or other phytoplasmas in symptomatic plants (Bertaccini *et al.*, 2019; Luis-Pantoja *et al.*, 2021) indicating that in this specific ecosystem citrus could be an alternative host species for LY phytoplasmas. In Mexico transmission trials of 16SrIV phytoplasmas with adults of *Haplaxius crudus* to *Pritchardia pacifica* plants confirmed its vector role in this country (Narvaez *et al.*, 2019; Dzido *et al.*, 2020). Dwarf coconut varieties that showed promising results (Figure 4) in relation to LY resistance are under evaluation in trials in Ghana (Quaicoe *et al.*, 2009), compared with a susceptible variety and a hybrid used for replanting. In Mexico different palm ecotypes are studied to determine their resistance to LY using a molecular marker able to distinguish the susceptible palm ecotypes. LAMP diagnostic systems for detecting LY phytoplasmas from Africa and from the Caribbean are under development, while qPCR assays for 16SrIV phytoplasmas were specifically applied (Córdova *et al.*, 2020).

Grapevine yellows

The grapevine yellows (GY) associated phytoplasmas are well known in Europe, while less data and

Figure 4. Measurement of collar girth (left) and fertilization to maximize the potential of the palms (right) (L. Arhin, E.N. Yankey, CSIR-OPRI, Ghana).

information are available for other countries, such as Chile and South Africa where disease is having similar symptomatology with different degrees of severity according to the phytoplasma, its strain or to the grapevine cultivar (Figure 5).

In South Africa, the phytoplasmas associated with GY are ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related vectored by *Mgenia fuscovaria* (Smyth *et al.*, 2015; Krüger *et al.*, 2011; 2015; Coetzee *et al.*, 2019) therefore a management plan for this phytoplasma has been developed including recommendations for leafhopper monitoring, weed control, sanitation and chemical control.

In Chile different grapevine phytoplasmas and insects harboring some of these phytoplasmas have

Figure 5. Top row: vineyards severely infected with yellows (A. Angelini, CREA, Italy). Bottom row: main yellows symptoms in grapevine including irregular yellowing or reddening in white and red cultivars, respectively, downward curling very often with a triangle shape of the leaves, shortened internodes, death of tips and shoots, lack of lignification, aborting flowers, shrivelling and early drying of berries (A. Bertaccini, UNIBO, Italy and N. Fiore UCHIL, Chile).

been identified and, during the project, the prevalent phytoplasmas resulted those related to ‘*Ca. P. pruni*’ enclosed in the ribosomal subgroup 16SrIII-J. These phytoplasmas were also detected in five previously unreported plant species (*Rosa* spp., *Brassica rapa*, *Erodium* spp., *Malva* spp. and *Rubus ulmifolius*) growing in the infected vineyards (Quiroga *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, it also was demonstrated that the 16SrIII-J phytoplasma is transmitted to grapevine and periwinkle by the insects *Paratanus exitiosus* and *Bergallia valdiviana* (Quiroga *et al.*, 2019).

In the majority of the European countries, the GY diseases most spread are “bois noir” and “flavescence dorée”, associated respectively with ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ (16SrXII-A) and “flavescence dorée” strains 16SrV-C and -D (Martini *et al.*, 1999, Botti and Bertaccini, 2007), the last one being a quarantine organism (Angelini *et al.*, 2018). Surveys in selected north Italy vineyards detected ‘*Ca. P. solani*’, ‘*Ca. P. fraxini*’, ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ and “flavescence dorée” phytoplasmas and new potential insect vectors (Zambon *et al.*, 2018). In the area of Treviso province (Prosecco wine), the presence of alternative plant species for the three main phytoplasmas detected in the grapevine with yellows such as 16SrXII-A, 16SrI and 16SrV was reported (Table 1). Similar surveys allowed to verify the presence of new potential plant host and insect vector species, and of diverse phytoplasmas in known insect vector species (Paltrinieri *et al.*, 2019). The plant species infected with 16SrXII-A phytoplasmas are confirming or increasing the list of the several host plant species harboring as possible source of infection this phytoplasma in vineyards and in several other agricultural and natural environments (Table 1).

The ELISA test using phytoplasma Imp protein as antigen was proven to be a reliable tool to specifically detect the FD presence in symptomatic grapevine plants. It works also for testing the main phytoplasma vector *Scaphoideus titanus*, and *Alnus glutinosa* and *Clematis vitalba* alternative host plants (Filippin *et al.*, 2019; Trivellone *et al.*, 2019). This ELISA test might be used in the monitoring programs as a preliminary screening of large number of samples; the samples resulting negative can then be tested by more sensitive or specific molecular methods such as qPCR or nested

Table 1. Phytoplasma identified in insects and alternative host plants in and around vineyards in Italy (in parenthesis phytoplasmas already reported).

Insect species	Phytoplasma identified
<i>Scaphoideus titanus</i>	16SrI-B (16SrV-C, 16SrXII-A)
<i>Hyalestes obsoletus</i>	16SrI-B (16SrXII-A)
<i>Orientus ishidae</i>	16SrI-B (16SrV-C, 16SrXII-A)
<i>Neoliturus fenestratus</i>	16SrI (16SrXII-A)
Plant species	Phytoplasma identified
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Calystegia sepium</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Clematis vitalba</i>	16SrV, 16SrI
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Rosa canina</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Conyza canadensis</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Hedera helix</i>	16SrI
<i>Partenocissus quinquefolia</i>	16SrXII-A
<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	16SrI
<i>Rubus</i> spp.	16SrI
<i>Morus</i> spp.	16SrI
<i>Convolvulus</i> spp.	16SrXII-A
<i>Quercus</i> spp.	16SrXII-A

PCR, respectively. Furthermore, grapevine aster yellows antibodies raised from phytoplasma colonies (Contaldo *et al.*, 2016) were tested by ELISA and IFAS methods to evaluate their suitability for phytoplasma detection in plant samples. The two methods showed a good specificity to the aster yellows phytoplasma cultures, while the IFAS assay gave promising results also with infected plant tissues (Contaldo *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusions

It is therefore clear that only a constant monitoring will allow the prompt detection of known or new phytoplasmas that may infect the studied crops. Furthermore, monitoring is necessary to determine if endemic and/or new phytoplasmas and phytoplasma strains are spreading. Appropriate management is linked to the diverse geographical locations and agroecosystem conditions, but with the appropriate epidemiologic knowledge it can be applied as a sustainable tool to reduce the economic losses and the environmental pollution.

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